

A New Performance Metric for Hybrid Adaptive Optics Systems

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Abstract—Advances in Adaptive Optics (AO) systems and image processing techniques have allowed image reconstruction to reach new levels of sophistication with impressive improvements in resolvability. The products of these reconstruction methods are often compared by eye due to a lack of widely agreed-upon objective performance metrics. This paper describes a new technique for assessing the performance of image reconstruction algorithms and AO systems. A line spread function is extracted from an object's edges, and the full width at half maximum of this experimentally measured line spread function is compared to the full width at half maximum of the system's diffraction-limited line spread function. This technique is used with imagery of satellites taken with the 3.6m Maui AEOS telescope with and without an AO system and with image post-processing. The AO system in question allows for rapid switching between compensated and uncompensated imagery, so an objective comparison between the two is possible.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Hybrid Adaptive Optics (HAO) systems combine an Adaptive Optics (AO) system with advanced image processing techniques in order to achieve greater resolution than what is achievable by either system alone. The use of quality metrics allows for comparisons to be made between HAO systems and their experimental improvements. The most common method for judging HAO image results historically has been subjective viewing of the images. Full reference metrics such as the Information Theoretic Image Quality Equation (ITIQUE) require a pristine example of the imaging target and are not applicable to evaluation of

field data [1,2]. The Strehl ratio is the traditional measure of AO performance, but it has several shortcomings when applied to HAO systems: it requires a point source target, which may not be available in scenarios of interest; the image processing stage can oversharpen, leading to exaggerated scores; and under some circumstances the Strehl ratio is not a reliable predictor of image quality [3]. Other no-reference metrics tend to have poor sensitivity when applied to the types of iterative deconvolution algorithms that are commonly used in HAO systems [4].

An image quality metric that can be experimentally measured on a wide variety of objects is critical for comparing resolution improvement techniques. An ideal metric is objective, applicable to a variety of imaging targets, and can be compared to a physically ideal value without the use of reference images. One such solution is introduced here in the form of a technique for extracting the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of a Line Spread Function (LSF) from an edge on an extended object. Section 2 describes the technique for measuring the LSF from an extended object's edge, Section 3 describes other metrics that were examined for comparison to the LSF extraction results, Section 4 describes experimental measurements of the LSF FWHM and other metrics, and Section 5 contains a discussion of conclusions and future work.

2. LINE SPREAD FUNCTION MEASUREMENT

When examining the edges of a reconstructed image by eye, subjectively "better" images tend to have sharply-defined edges. A counts distribution passing perpendicularly through an edge on an extended object can be characterized as a line spread function (LSF) convolved with a Heaviside function centered at the point of maximum slope in the data (defined as C).

$$Data(\theta) = LSF(\theta) \otimes H(\theta - C) \quad (1)$$

The LSF is an interesting function from which one can extract meaningful image quality information. The full

Figure 1 – Observed SEASAT satellite data with a line drawn perpendicular to an edge along one of the panels. The distribution of counts along this line is extracted from the image with cubic spline interpolation. This distribution is plotted alongside a parameterized Heaviside function that has been fitted to the data.

width at half maximum (FWHM) of the LSF is an indicator of image quality at the examined edge, and it is relatively straightforward to calculate the FWHM of the diffraction-limited LSF of an imaging system for purposes of comparison. The diffraction-limited LSF is obtained by integrating the diffraction-limited point spread function (PSF) along one axis [5] in units of $R = \theta D/\lambda$.

$$PSF(R) = 4 \left(\frac{J_1(\pi R)}{\pi R} \right)^2 \quad (2)$$

$$LSF(x) = \frac{3}{4} \int_0^\infty \left(\frac{J_1(\pi \sqrt{x^2 + y^2})}{\sqrt{x^2 + y^2}} \right)^2 dy \quad (3)$$

Equation 3 has no analytical form, but it can be integrated numerically. One finds that the FWHM of the LSF is approximately λ/D .

The ratio of the FWHM of the experimentally measured LSF to the FWHM of the diffraction-limited LSF is a measurement of how close a HAO system has come to producing a diffraction-limited image. If the measured LSF FWHM varies significantly at different edges on the same image, then this can be an indicator of localized image degradation caused by optical aberrations such as dispersion.

Attempting to deconvolve a Heaviside function from the data directly can be problematic. The deconvolution is performed in discretized Fourier space using numerical techniques. Noisy data or data that does not fully describe an LSF convolved with a Heaviside function can introduce undesirable spatial frequency fluctuations. The data would also need to be smoothed with a windowing function in

order to eliminate edge effects. Instead, a parameterized function can be fitted to the edge distribution and then mirrored. A simplified form of the generalized logistic function (GLF) is used for this purpose.

$$F(\theta) = A + \frac{B - A}{1 + e^{-d(\theta - C)}} \quad (4)$$

This form of the GLF has many advantages. Its lower and upper asymptotes are defined by parameters A and B , respectively. The parameter C sets the midpoint of the growth curve, allowing the function to be fitted along an axis with arbitrarily-defined units. Conveniently, this parameter also coincides with the midpoint of the Heaviside function that must be deconvolved from the GLF in order to obtain the LSF in Equation 1. Parameter d dictates the function's growth rate; flipping the sign of d reverses the function, and as d approaches 0 the slope of the function approaches 0. As d becomes very large, it starts to behave like a Heaviside function. Examples of the GLF with various fixed parameters are shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3, and Figure 4 shows examples of a mirrored Heaviside function and a mirrored GLF fitted to real data.

Figure 2 – Examples of the generalized logistic function with fixed values for parameters A, B, and C

Figure 3 – Examples of the generalized logistic function with fixed values for parameters A, B, and d

Figure 4 – Observed SEASAT satellite data with a line drawn perpendicular to an edge along one of the panels. The distribution of counts along this line is extracted from the image with cubic spline interpolation. A GLF (Equation 4) is fitted to the data and then mirrored. A Heaviside function is fitted to the data and also mirrored.

Assuming that the GLF in Equation 1 is a reasonably accurate description of an object’s edge, then the Data in Equation 1 is replaced with the GLF that was fitted to the data.

$$GLF(\theta) = LSF(\theta) \otimes H(\theta - C) \quad (5)$$

Using Weiner Deconvolution [6], it is possible to measure the FWHM of the LSF using any arbitrarily chosen edge on an extended object. Furthermore, the ratio of the LSF FWHM before and after some improvement-providing effect, such as AO compensation or image processing, provides a quantitative estimate of how much the visual quality of that edge has improved.

3. OTHER METRICS

This new image quality metric is compared to three other image quality metrics: Muller and Buffington’s S2 metric (Sharpness) [7], Sobel Edge Moment (SEM) Variance [8], and Laplacian of Gaussian (LoG) [9]. Sharpness is the sum of squares of the pixel values of the image (where the image is denoted as Z) divided by the squared sum of the image’s pixel values.

$$M_S = \frac{\sum_i \sum_j Z_{ij}^2}{(\sum_i \sum_j Z_{ij})^2} \quad (6)$$

The SEM Variance is the variance of the image’s gradient. The gradient can be approximated by convolving the image with Sobel edge operators, and the variance of this result is the metric of interest.

$$S_x = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 & 1 \\ -2 & 0 & 2 \\ -1 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

$$S_y = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & -2 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 2 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

$$M_{SEM} = var \left(\sqrt{(S_x \otimes Z)_{ij}^2 + (S_y \otimes Z)_{ij}^2} \right) \quad (9)$$

The LoG metric is calculated by convolving the image with a Laplacian of Gaussian filter and then taking the sum of the modulus square of the image’s pixels. This work uses a LoG spatial filter of size 10 and $\sigma = 0.5$.

$$h_g(x, y) = \nabla^2 \left(\exp \left\{ \frac{-(x^2 + y^2)}{2\sigma^2} \right\} \right) \quad (10)$$

$$M_{LoG} = \sum_i \sum_j |(h_g \otimes Z)_{ij}|^2 \quad (11)$$

These metrics each provide objective estimates of a system’s imaging performance, and the ratio of each metric’s value before and after processing or compensation can be treated as an estimate of improvement. These metrics all evaluate the average quality of the entire image rather than specific parts of the image; the LSF FWHM extraction method described in Section 2 is not only able to evaluate the quality of specific image sections, but it can be used on multiple edges in order to obtain an average LSF FWHM.

4. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Calibrated images of several extended objects were taken with the AEOS 3.6m telescope with and without the AO system. Objects are post-processed with one of two versions of a physically constrained iterative deconvolution image reconstruction algorithm: PCID [10,11] or PCID_Fast. These two versions differ in that PCID_Fast is a faster algorithm but tends to produce worse results than PCID. Simple corner bias subtraction is applied to the calibrated and post-processed imagery.

The calculation of the LSF begins when a line segment is chosen that is perpendicular to an edge on the object. Third order spline interpolation is used to extract the pixel values along this line segment. In an attempt to minimize bias effects, the line segment pixel values are recalculated for ± 1 and ± 2 pixel shifts along the object edge, and the median pixels between these five lines are chosen as the set of points along which the GLF is extracted. The angle of the line segment is allowed to vary within a ± 5 degree cone, and Equation 1 is fitted to the data with a Levenberg-Marquardt non-linear least squares algorithm [12,13] until a best fit is found.

The GLF is assumed to be a Heaviside function convolved with a LSF, as shown in Equation 2. In order to eliminate edge effects influencing the Fourier transforms, the GLF and the Heaviside function are each mirrored such that the ends of each distribution are a minimum, and then the entire distribution is reduced by this minimum. Wiener Deconvolution [4] is used to extract the LSF from these two distributions, and then the FWHM is extracted from the LSF. Results of this method are shown in Figure 5 through Figure 14. All pixel lengths have been scaled by an arbitrary constant.

The ratio of the LSF FWHM before PCID processing to after PCID processing provides an estimate of the improvement that the PCID or PCID_Fast algorithm provides to the imagery. This ratio is compared to the improvement measured by the Sharpness, Sobel Variance, and LoG metrics. These full-frame non-reference metrics are designed to be larger for better images, whereas the LSF FWHM is smaller for better images. Thus, these full-frame metric ratios have been inverted such that a ratio greater than one indicates an improvement in image quality and less than one indicates degradation.

Table 1 shows all of the measured PCID and PCID_Fast improvement ratios versus RAW (uncompensated) data and AO compensated data. Several interesting observations can be made from this table. First, the SEM Variance and LoG appear to vary considerably and do not provide any consistency when ratios are analyzed. Sharpness appears to be a little more consistent, but only marginally so. The LSF FWHM ratio appears to be more consistent than any of the full-image metrics; the PCID_Fast algorithm shows an

improvement between 1.09 and 1.26, a relatively narrow band compared to 1.23 to 2.00 for Sharpness.

The slower PCID algorithm appears to cause discrepancies in the measured correction between SEASAT edges; the algorithm is padding the PCID-reconstructed edges with a long intensity falloff, and this causes the GLF fit to be poor. This effect is absent in the AO cases. The AO vs. AO + PCID comparison using SEASAT consistently shows an improvement around 2 for both of the panels because effects like dispersion have already been removed by the AO system.

Table 2 shows all of the measured AO improvement ratios. These values could only be calculated for the SEASAT pass, as it was taken in a mode that made it possible to take near-simultaneous AO-compensated and raw uncompensated data. The PCID algorithm once again creates a discrepancy between edges in the PCID reconstruction of RAW images due to intensity padding around the image, so the RAW PCID vs. AO PCID results are not very reliable as an indicator of AO performance. In the RAW uncompensated vs. AO compensated comparison, the AO system appears to provide an improvement around 3. When PCID is applied, the improvement is between around 1.5 and 3.2 depending on the edge chosen.

Table 1 – The ratio of various metrics before PCID or PCID_Fast processing to after processing; values greater than one indicate improvement. Edge A and Edge B refer to different edge locations on the image.

Satellite	Sharp ratio	SEM Var ratio	LoG ratio	LSF FWHM ratio
SEASAT RAW / PCID of RAW	1.46	7.95	9.06	Edge A: 1.92 Edge B: 3.78
SEASAT AO / PCID of AO	1.17	5.54	7.07	Edge A: 2.01 Edge B: 2.08
GLAST horizontal AO / PCID_Fast of AO	2.00	1.34	1.22	Edge A: 1.21 Edge B: 1.16
GLAST vertical AO / PCID_Fast of AO	1.38	2.08	4.85	Edge A: 1.14 Edge B: 1.09
IRIDIUM36 RAW / PCID_Fast of RAW	1.23	1.13	1.85	Edge A: 1.26 Edge B: 1.23

Table 2 – The ratio of various metrics with and without AO compensation; values greater than one indicate improvement. Edge A and Edge B refer to different edge locations on the image.

Satellite	Sharp ratio	SEM Var ratio	LoG ratio	LSF FWHM ratio
SEASAT RAW / AO	1.47	5.52	5.11	Edge A: 3.08 Edge B: 3.05
SEASAT PCID of RAW / PCID of AO	1.19	3.84	3.99	Edge A: 3.2 Edge B: 1.68

Figure 5 – SEASAT recordings with the AO system turned off, before and after PCID processing. The LSF was extracted from a panel in the upper region of the image.

Figure 6 – SEASAT recordings with the AO system turned off, before and after PCID processing. The LSF was extracted from a panel in the lower region of the image.

Figure 7 – SEASAT recordings with the AO system turned on, before and after PCID processing. The LSF was extracted from a panel in the upper region of the image.

Figure 8 – SEASAT recordings with the AO system turned on, before and after PCID processing. The LSF was extracted from a panel in the upper region of the image.

Figure 9 – GLAST recordings with the AO system turned on, before and after PCID processing, where GLAST is in a horizontal orientation. The LSF was extracted from a panel in the left region of the image.

Figure 10 – GLAST recordings with the AO system turned on, before and after PCID processing, where GLAST is in a horizontal orientation. The LSF was extracted from a panel in the right region of the image.

Figure 11 – GLAST recordings with the AO system turned on, before and after PCID processing, where GLAST is in a vertical orientation. The LSF was extracted from a panel in the lower region of the image.

Figure 12 – GLAST recordings with the AO system turned on, before and after PCID processing, where GLAST is in a vertical orientation. The LSF was extracted from a panel in the upper region of the image.

Figure 13 – Iridium 36 recordings with the AO system turned off, before and after PCID processing. The LSF was extracted from a panel in the lower region of the image.

Figure 14 – Iridium 36 recordings with the AO system turned off, before and after PCID processing. The LSF was extracted from a panel in the upper region of the image.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

A new metric has been presented that can be used in evaluating the edge reconstruction resolution of an imaging system. This metric involves taking the distribution of counts passing through a line perpendicular to the edge of an object, fitting this distribution to a generalized logistic function, deconvolving a Heaviside function from the result, and then extracting the full width at half max from the resulting distribution. This method shows better consistency in measuring the improvement of PCID_Fast reconstructions than the Sharpness, Sobel Edge Moment, or Laplacian of Gradient methods. The slower PCID algorithm, which is applied to all of the SEASAT passes, produces greater variations in all of the examined metrics. It may be possible to design a function that fits better to these cases. Not enough simultaneous AO-speckle examples were taken for a conclusive judgment, but the results so far look promising for a metric based on LSF extraction from edges. Additional simultaneous AO-speckle data should be taken and all of these metrics should be assessed in additional comparative studies.

The LSF FWHM edge extraction method is objective and consistent between the tested objects, and the choice of edge does not appear to strongly influence the estimated FWHM in the PCID_Fast examples or between AO and speckle. The standard PCID examples produce some large variations, possibly due to how dispersion was being handled by the slower algorithm. This demonstrates that the LSF FWHM metric is especially useful in analyzing the improvement that AO or post-processing systems might be providing to specific regions of an image rather than the image as a whole.

Most importantly, the experimentally extracted LSF FWHM can be compared to the diffraction-limited LSF FWHM, a simple to calculate and theoretically relevant value for any imaging system. This makes the LSF FWHM edge extraction method unique among the no-reference objective imaging metrics presented here in that its results are relatable to a physical quantity.

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BIOGRAPHY

Michael Werth received a BS in Physics from the University of Arizona in 2007 and a Ph.D. in Physics from UC Irvine in 2012. Most of his undergraduate and graduate career was spent at CERN working with the Large Hadron Collider's ATLAS Detector searching for fourth generation quarks and working with data acquisition systems. Now Michael is a Boeing engineer and imaging scientist with research interests that include image reconstruction, sensor development, and high-performance computing.

Brandoch Calef is an imaging scientist with Boeing. For ten years, he has supported the AFRL space surveillance site on Maui. His research interests include image reconstruction, atmospheric statistics, estimation theory, optical instrumentation, and high-performance computing. He received a PhD in Applied Mathematics from the University of California Berkeley.

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Skip Williams received joint BS degrees in Chemistry and Physics from the University of Arkansas in 1988 and a Ph.D. in Chemical Physics from Stanford University in 1994. Part of his Ph.D. thesis work was completed at the Sandia National Laboratories, and he started his research career with a Postdoctoral appointment at Los Alamos National Laboratory from 1994-1996. Since 1996, he has conducted research at the Air Force Research Laboratory and is currently the Chief Engineer at the Air Force Maui Optical and Supercomputing (AMOS) site. His current research focusses on inverse synthetic aperture LADAR for imaging space assets beyond the normal resolvable range of optics based on aperture diameter encompassing electro-optics, laser propagation, adaptive optics, and signal processing activities.